

FORESIGHT AS A TOOL FOR "SMART" REGIONAL SPECIALIZATION

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Currently, one of the main indicators that determine the competitiveness of a region is not concerned with its size, but with its ability to create inventions and innovations taking into consideration its unique features and economics date of a region. Therefore, the systematic base of innovation economy in a country should be based on innovation policy concerned with the distinctive features and advantages of one region from another. Under the conditions of international global competition, developing regions follow the "powerful development" of socio-economically developed regions and try to directly repeat and copy the "model" of creating and introducing innovations. By directly repeating "growth models" regions carry out unsuccessful and counterproductive work because they do not take into account the region's strengths and weaknesses, opportunities and threats.

With this on mind, the "smart" program of specialization for regions was created to solve the problem of "not repeating others". "Smart specialization" is a program to develop the region based on its natural and raw material resources, ecological and climatic features, human capital, and all the advantages that distinguish it from other regions, based on innovative technologies in those areas.

Foresight research is an effective tool to protect and avoid obstacles and limitations, implementing the regions' raw materials, climate characteristics, development potential, level of human capital supply, entrepreneurship, innovative and investment capacity, regional infrastructure to the fullest.

Foresight being a technology to build the future is a set of studies used systematically to build an everlasting future, taking into account possible reforms in all spheres of life: science and education, economy, social relations and culture, with the participation of all experts and stakeholders.

Representatives of various industries participate in Foresight studies. They are representatives of scientific and technological organizations, entrepreneurship, government and societal entities.

An average of 6-10 inspection methods are used per Foresight. The choice of audit methods depends on the project, organization, circumstance, budget, availability of experts, or intended purpose. Looking at the international experience, for example Japan, the Delphi method was used to make a technological forecast for the next 30 years, in Great Britain and Germany, a wide range of methods and their mix were used, and in the United States and France, it was widely used to make a list of technologies of great importance.

Methods for conducting foresight research require specific conditions, information, technologies, or expertise. In this paper, the opportunities of using the methods of Foresight research set under the conditions of Turkmenistan were analyzed.

As a result, methods such as bibliometrics, patents and literature analysis are currently not fully utilized due to the scarcity of data, on the other hand benchmarking, extrapolation of trends, brainstorming, citizen and expert panels, STEP and SWOT analysis, implementation of Delphi and a list of important technologies methods is possible and could be carried out under the beneficial conditions.

Some of the most effective methods include Delphi, technology priority lists, scenario building, technological roadmaps, and expert panels.

There is no specific sequence or set interrelations of methods used in foresight studies, and each region chooses it based on its own goals and capabilities.

The cost of conducting foresight inspections depends on the area being inspected, the size of the inspection, the time and methods used.

Basic costs are made up of:

- funding of the project management team;
- holding meetings and events expenses;
- advertising expenses;
- additional expenses.

In conclusion, the foresight research is the most effective method implemented to develop the region by bringing together experts from different business types, authorities and citizens' opinions.